

Effect of Surface Area on the Dehydroxylation Kinetics of Kaolinite Mineral

N. K. MITRA* and S. MAITRA

Department of Chemical Technology, Calcutta University, 92, A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 20 November 1992, accepted 29 January 1993

Kinetics of thermal dehydroxylation of kaolinite clay mineral has been studied as a function of its surface area. The kinetic parameters have been correlated with the surface area and a mathematical relationship has been developed between the activation energy of dehydroxylation and the surface area of the clay.

Kinetic studies on kaolinite were performed by various workers. Murry and White¹ showed that isothermal decomposition of the clay mineral proceeds according to the first order kinetics. Birch-Holt *et al.*² found that at pressure near 1 mm Hg, the dehydration of kaolinite is diffusion-controlled. Criado *et al.*³ explained why different investigators have ascribed both first order kinetics and diffusion mechanism to the dehydroxylation of kaolinite. Stoch⁴ studied the significance of structural factors in dehydroxylation of kaolinite. Lesker *et al.*⁵ studied the kinetics and mechanism of dehydroxylation of kaolinite by DTA.

Present investigation was undertaken to study systematically the kinetics of thermal decomposition of kaolinite as a function of surface area. The basis for the understanding of the rate process was the Arrhenius relationship which states that for many processes the logarithm of reaction rate constant is proportional to the reciprocal of absolute temperature. The relative influence of the surface area on dehydration was compared by carrying out isothermal experiments under identical conditions and determining kinetic parameters for the expulsion of hydroxyl water from

the lattice.

Results and Discussion

China clay was thoroughly purified from the associated impurities and converted to monoionic sodium form. Chemical analysis (Table 1) of the different size fractions indicated the presence of free silica in the form of quartz in the coarser fractions. The amount of residual Fe₂O₃ in the purified clay followed a direct relationship with the particle size which might be due to positioning of iron within the grain. Positive variation of DTA peak temperatures (Table 1) was observed. With the increase of surface area, the crystallinity decreased as a result of which decomposition and crystallisation rates increased. After characterising the different fractions they were subjected to isothermal dehydration study for examining the kinetics of the process. The clay samples were always taken in the form of loose powder where the expulsion of the formed water was not restricted artificially.

The plot of weight-loss against time showed exponential behaviour (figure not shown) which suggested the application of first order kinetics. Applying

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND THERMAL DATA OF DIFFERENT FRACTIONS OF KAOLINITE

Sample no.	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹	Analysis %				Molar ratio SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ †	DTA peak temp. °C	
		SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	L.O.I.		Endo	Exo
1	3.1	48.98	38.12	0.72	12.04	2.18	600	1 080
2	5.4	48.22	38.52	0.72	12.04	2.13	590	1 040
3	8.4	47.33	39.20	0.68	12.06	2.05	590	1 070
4	9.6	47.18	39.49	0.67	12.06	2.04	590	1 050
5	12.6	46.55	39.49	0.64	12.03	2.00	590	1 030
6	19.2	46.40	39.84	0.63	12.95	1.98	560	1 020

Guggenheim's kinetic equation⁶ in the following form,

$$\log \Delta L = (-K_1/2.303) + \log L_\alpha / 1 - \exp(-K_1 \Delta t)$$

the reaction rate constants (K_1) and the equilibrium weight-loss (L_α) were calculated (Table 2). From the results of the isothermal study, $\log \Delta L$ was plotted against time (figure not shown). Perfect linearity was maintained for all the samples indicating the justification of the application of first order kinetics.

During dehydroxylation of clays the basic structure was always affected and the change was found to be irreversible. The dehydrated layer acted as a dif-

fusion barrier to this process. Surface areas of the original clay samples exhibited positive influence in increasing the rate of reaction. In case of diffusion-controlled reaction, it is obvious that diffusion path is normally shortened if the particle size is decreased. Equilibrium weight-loss values increased with the increase in surface area (Table 2) which might be due to the increase in surface charge. This was a consequence of broken bond theory and the increased surface charge neutralised itself by combining with excess OH group from outer systems. Thus the number of OH groups per unit area of the surface increased with the increase

TABLE 2—VALUES OF K_1 , K_2 , L_α AND PERCENT VALIDITY OF FIRST KINETICS DURING DEHYDROXYLATION OF KAOLINITE

Surface area m^2g^{-1}	Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	K_1	K_2	L_α	Percent validity
3.1	540	0.024	0.005	0.006	50.12
	570	0.112	0.006	0.336	53.37
	600	0.158	0.008	0.454	55.12
	630	0.398	0.012	0.766	67.07
	660	0.631	0.015	0.783	72.33
	690	1.059	0.019	0.961	74.12
5.4	540	0.038	0.005	0.141	51.90
	570	0.133	0.006	0.408	53.67
	600	0.266	0.010	0.662	58.50
	630	0.501	0.014	0.722	69.69
	660	0.668	0.017	0.755	74.65
	690	1.497	0.020	0.962	80.28
8.4	540	0.052	0.006	0.120	55.63
	570	0.150	0.006	0.602	64.45
	600	0.282	0.010	0.743	67.31
	630	0.501	0.005	0.858	76.08
	660	0.749	0.016	0.900	79.75
	690	1.567	0.022	0.991	84.63
9.6	540	0.084	0.006	0.363	60.77
	570	0.237	0.006	0.758	65.18
	600	0.376	0.010	0.854	69.88
	630	0.708	0.015	0.943	79.41
	660	1.122	0.018	0.979	80.78
	690	1.679	0.030	0.986	86.26
12.6	540	0.114	0.006	0.682	62.58
	570	0.299	0.006	0.888	66.61
	600	0.531	0.012	0.893	70.18
	630	0.891	0.017	0.910	79.55
	660	1.189	0.020	0.978	82.53
	690	1.883	0.030	0.994	86.64
19.2	540	0.187	0.007	0.928	63.35
	570	0.447	0.010	0.928	68.25
	600	0.708	0.014	0.943	72.94
	630	1.122	0.020	0.977	81.37
	660	1.496	0.029	0.979	83.40
	690	2.371	0.036	0.999	87.18

in surface area.

Kaolinite with maximum surface area showed minimum temperature dependence with respect to L_α values (Table 2) which might be correlated with excess residual energy in the system causing higher amplitude of vibration of the OH groups.

The full course of the dehydroxylation reaction did not follow first order kinetics and the extent of validity was determined from the linearity of plots of $\log(L_\alpha - L)/L_\alpha$ against time. Percent validity (Table 2) was found to increase with increase in surface area and it revealed that about 87% of the dehydration reaction followed first order kinetics. This can be explained in the way that the dehydration reaction was mostly diffusion-controlled and during the process water molecules were evaporated by bulk diffusion giving a dehydrated instable network of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 . The rate of dehydration depends on the loss of water from the interface between the original hydrate and dehydrated product and this was proportional to temperature and surface area.

The reaction rate constants (K_2) at the final stage of dehydration were calculated⁶ (Table 2). K_2 values were found to be always lower than the corresponding K_1 values and were also dependent on temperature. At the latter stage of dehydration, the concentration of reacting molecules decreased and the diffusion path increased because of the formation of a thicker dehydrated layer. Moreover, the movement of the water molecules across the path was inhibited by the lattice shrinkage.

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION ENERGIES AS DETERMINED FROM ARRHENIUS PLOT OF KAOLINITES DURING DEHYDROXYLATION

Sample no.	Activation energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)		E_2/E_1 during expulsion of water
	Initial stage E_1	Final stage E_2	
1	44.57	51.56	1.1568
2	41.39	47.84	1.1558
3	37.15	42.92	1.1553
4	34.48	39.65	1.1499
5	31.61	36.32	1.1490
6	29.29	33.62	1.1478

Finally, the activation energies both at the initial and final stages of dehydration were calculated from the usual Arrhenius plots. In each case E_2 value was greater than the corresponding E_1 value (Table 3) but the ratio of E_2/E_1 was found to be almost independent of surface area indicating some proportionality between the two reaction rates during the course of dehydration. With the decrease in surface area the activation energy has been brought down from 51 to 33 kcal mol⁻¹.

Plots of activation energies against surface area exhibited similar nature of curves (at both the initial and final stage of dehydration) as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig 1 Plots of activation energy against surface area (*) initial and (Δ) final.

By the best-fitting method two mathematical relationships were developed between surface area and the activation energies at the initial and final stages of dehydroxylation,

$$Y = -8.97114 \ln(X) + 55.399 \text{ (Initial stage)}$$

$$Y = -10.545 \ln(X) + 64.299 \text{ (Final stage)}$$

where Y and X indicate the activation energy and the surface area respectively.

Conclusions :

- (i) Though the crystallinity of kaolinite mineral was an inverse function of surface area but it was not sufficient enough to create amorphous characteristics.
- (ii) The dehydroxylation of kaolinite mineral followed

first order kinetics and was not a continuous process irrespective of surface area but the kinetic parameters were strongly influenced. In the later stage of dehydration the partially dehydrated structure was associated with the collapse of the lattice and blocking of the reaction sites. (iii) The final correlation between activation energy and surface area has been worked out as

$$Y = -8.97114 \ln(X) + 55.399 \text{ (Initial stage)}$$

$$Y = -10.545 \ln(X) + 64.299 \text{ (Final stage)}$$

where Y is the activation energy and X the surface area.

Experimental

Rajmahal (Bihar) China clay was selected for the present investigation. The clay was purified from its associated impurities and was converted into monoionic sodium form⁷. The clay was then fractionated into six different size fractions following gravity sedimentation technique. All the samples were chemically analysed. Differential thermal analysis was

carried out with a Netzsch Geratebau GmbH self thermal analyser. Surface area was determined by a Carle Erba Strumentazione instrument which was based on gas adsorption BET principle. Kinetics of thermal dehydroxylation of the samples in the powder form were performed with a thermobalance.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.M.) expresses his acknowledgement to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. P. MURRAY and J. WHITE, *Trans. Br. Ceram. Soc.*, 1985, **54**, 151.
2. J. BIRCHHILL, IVAN, B. CUTLER and M. E. WADSWORTH, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1962, **45**, 133.
3. J. M. CRIADO, A. ORTIGA, C. RIAL and E. TORRES, *Clay Miner.*, 1984, 653.
4. L. STOCH, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1984, **29**, 919.
5. Z. LISKIE, L. L. STOCH and I. WACLAWSKA, *Pr. Mineral.*, 1979, **59**, 59.
6. N. K. MITRA, K. J. ROY and S. MITRA, *Trans. Br. Ceram. Soc.*, 1975, **74**, 263.
7. N. K. MITRA, R. GHOSH DAS HIDAR and R. K. MONDOL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 747.